

Modeling of *Clostridium histolyticum* collagenase inhibitory activity of some sulfonyl-1-amine hydroxamates : A molecular connectivity approach

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Abstract : Topological modeling of protease inhibitory activity of some sulfonyl-1-amine hydroxamates which are known to be *Clostridium histolyticum* collagenase inhibitors has been presented in this paper. Out of the pool of topological indices used Randic and Kier-Hall connectivity indices are found most suitable for the modeling of inhibitory activity.

Keywords : ChC inhibitors, protease inhibitors, QSAR, connectivity indices, topological modeling.

Introduction

The nuclear substituted derivatives of hydroxamic acid are found to behave as inhibitors against *Clostridium histolyticum* collagenase. Some of the derivatives of hydroxamic acid are found to inhibit DNA synthesis by inactivating the enzyme ribonucleotide reductase (RNR)¹⁻³. Scozzafava and Supuran¹ have reported some protease inhibitors which are hydroxamates obtained by the reaction of *N*-(4-nitrobenzyl)-2-alanine with alkyl arylsulfonyl halides. In their paper they have reported ChC (*Clostridium histolyticum* collagenase) inhibitory activity of these compounds. It is worth mentioning that ChC (EC 3.4.24.3) is a zinc protein belonging to the Mg metalloproteinase family⁴ being able to hydrolyse triple helical regions of collagen under physiological conditions.

Scozzafava and coworkers¹ have reported some new compounds which are hydroxamates and are 100-500 times more active as ChC inhibitors as compared to the corresponding carboxylic acids. This was due to the enhanced Zn^{II} corresponding properties of the CONHOH moiety

(bidentate binding) as compared to -COOH group (generally monodentate binding to the zinc ion). In our present communication, we have chosen 49 compounds reported by Scozzafava *et al.*¹ and the structural details of these compounds are shown in Table 1. A perusal of this table

Table 1. Structural details of the compounds used in the present study

Compd.	Substituents (R)
1	CH ₃
2	CF ₃
3	CCl ₃
4	<i>n</i> -C ₄ F ₉ -
5	<i>n</i> -C ₈ F ₁₇ -
6	Me ₂ N-
7	C ₆ H ₅ -
8	PhCH ₂ -
9	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -
10	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -
11	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -

Table-1 (contd.)

- 12 4-I-C₆H₄-
- 13 4-CH₃-C₆H₄-
- 14 4-O₂N-C₆H₄-
- 15 3-O₂N-C₆H₄-
- 16 2-O₂N-C₆H₄-
- 17 3-Cl-4-O₂N-C₆H₃-
- 18 4-AcNH-C₆H₄-
- 19 4-BocNH-C₆H₄-
- 20 3-BocNH-C₆H₄-
- 21 4-Ac-C₆H₄-
- 22 C₆H₅-
- 23 3-CF₃-C₆H₄-
- 24 2,5-Cl₂-C₆H₃-
- 25 4-CH₃O-C₆H₄-
- 26 2,4,6-(CH₃)₃-C₆H₂-
- 27 4-CH₃O-3-BocNH-C₆H₃-
- 28 2-HO-3,5-Cl₂-C₆H₂-
- 29 3-HOOC-C₆H₄-
- 30 4-HOOC-C₆H₄-
- 31 1-Naphthyl
- 32 2-Naphthyl
- 33 5-Me₂N-1-naphthyl-
- 34 2-Thienyl
- 35 Quinoline-8-yl
- 36 4-F-C₆H₄-
- 37 4-Cl-C₆H₄-
- 38 4-CH₃-C₆H₄-
- 39 2-CH₃-C₆H₄-
- 40 4-F-C₆H₄-
- 41 3-Cl-C₆H₄-
- 42 4-Cl-C₆H₄-
- 43 2,4-F₂-C₆H₃-
- 44 3,4-Cl₂-C₆H₃-
- 45 1-Naphthyl
- 46 4-O₂N-C₆H₄-
- 47 2-O₂N-C₆H₄-
- 48 2,4-(O₂N)₂-C₆H₃-
- 49 J1

Structure B : Compd. 36-39

Structure C : Compd. 40-45

Structure D : Compd. 46-48

Structure E : Compd. 49 (J1)

shows that the following set of compounds show degeneracy : (a) 23, 30, 49; (b) 5, 31, 33, 37, 47; (c) 20, 27, 32, 35, 39; (d) 14, 19, 45; (e) 4, 18, 34, 46; (f) 15, 28, 38, 40; (g) 16, 24, 44; (h) 1, 2.

This clearly indicates that it is not possible to draw any logic which can explain the variation in log K_i activities with respect to their structure.

Modeling of activity (log K_i) : In order to obtain statistically significant models, the K_i (nM) values reported for 49 compounds by Scozzafava *et al.*¹ have been converted to their log units and are reported in Table 2. The method for calculation of various connectivity indices⁵⁻⁹ is given in the literature⁵. Topological indices viz. $^0\chi$, $^1\chi$, $^2\chi$, $^0\chi^v$, $^1\chi^v$, $^2\chi^v$ have been calculated using Dragon software. We have used an indicator parameter Ip_1 which accounts for the compounds which are derivatives of structure A (Table 1). Ip_1 is assigned a value of 1 if the compound is a derivative of structure A otherwise it is given a value of 0. The regression analysis has been performed on Regress-1 software using maximum R^2 method¹⁰. This software has been provided to us by Prof. Istvan Lukovits of Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest, Hungary.

Results and discussion

The correlation matrix for the correlation among various topological indices and log K_i is reported in Table 3. A close look at this table clearly indicates that strong co-linearity exists between (i) $^0\chi$ and $^1\chi$, (ii) $^0\chi$ and $^2\chi$, (iii) $^1\chi$ and $^2\chi$, (iv) $^1\chi$ and $^0\chi^v$, (v) $^0\chi^v$ and $^1\chi^v$, (vi) $^1\chi^v$ and $^2\chi^v$, (vii) $^0\chi$ and $^1\chi^v$, (viii) $^1\chi$ and $^1\chi^v$, (ix) $^2\chi$ and $^0\chi^v$, (x) $^0\chi^v$ and $^2\chi^v$.

In view of the above it becomes necessary to examine Randic recommendations for the existing of co-linearity. Randic^{11,12} stated that the selection of descriptors to be used in structure-property-activity studies should not be delegated solely to the computers, although the statistical criteria will continue to be useful for preliminary screen-

Table 2. Values of topological descriptors calculated and log K_i values for compounds (Table 1) used in the present study

Compd.	$^0\chi$	$^1\chi$	$^2\chi$	$^0\chi^v$	$^1\chi^v$	$^2\chi^v$	Ip_1	log K_i
1	16.21	9.66	9.48	12.20	7.65	6.32	1.00	1.88
2	18.11	10.91	11.08	12.84	7.61	6.45	1.00	1.88
3	18.11	10.91	11.08	15.10	8.14	9.56	1.00	1.72
4	26.21	14.66	15.96	16.60	9.49	8.22	1.00	1.04
5	33.11	18.41	20.83	20.37	11.38	9.94	1.00	0.85

Table-2 (contd)

6	11.78	10.61	10.09	13.65	7.87	7.01	1.00	1.84
7	19.32	12.27	11.27	14.59	8.98	7.33	1.00	1.73
8	20.03	12.74	11.81	15.30	9.56	7.78	1.00	1.70
9	20.19	12.66	11.89	14.89	9.05	7.47	1.00	1.54
10	20.19	12.66	11.89	15.65	9.43	7.91	1.00	1.51
11	20.19	12.66	11.89	16.48	9.85	8.39	1.00	1.48
12	20.19	12.66	11.89	17.05	10.13	8.72	1.00	1.57
13	20.19	12.66	11.89	15.51	9.36	7.83	1.00	1.56
14	21.77	13.57	12.79	15.78	9.45	7.77	1.00	1.00
15	21.77	13.57	12.80	15.78	9.45	7.77	1.00	1.08
16	21.77	13.59	12.73	15.78	9.46	7.71	1.00	1.11
17	22.64	13.98	13.33	16.83	9.94	8.29	1.00	0.95
18	23.18	14.56	13.62	17.33	10.23	8.24	1.00	1.04
19	25.68	15.74	15.76	19.83	11.48	10.17	1.00	1.00
20	25.68	15.74	15.76	19.83	11.48	10.17	1.00	0.90
21	22.47	14.06	13.28	16.83	9.98	8.08	1.00	0.95
22	23.67	14.34	13.75	16.56	10.23	8.90	1.00	0.70
23	22.69	13.87	13.86	16.15	9.68	8.04	1.00	0.78
24	21.06	13.07	12.44	16.70	9.91	8.40	1.00	1.11
25	20.90	13.20	12.06	15.92	9.48	7.69	1.00	1.32
26	21.93	13.48	12.99	17.36	10.20	8.68	1.00	1.23
27	27.26	16.69	16.48	21.16	12.01	10.51	1.00	0.90
28	21.93	13.48	11.95	17.07	10.05	8.56	1.00	1.08
29	21.77	13.57	12.80	15.87	9.54	7.85	1.00	0.95
30	21.77	13.57	12.79	15.87	9.54	7.85	1.00	0.78
31	21.89	14.25	13.18	16.74	10.36	8.46	1.00	0.85
32	21.89	14.25	13.18	16.74	10.36	8.46	1.00	0.90
33	24.34	15.57	14.64	19.11	11.40	9.51	1.00	0.85
34	18.61	11.77	10.91	14.66	9.32	8.12	1.00	1.04
35	21.89	14.25	13.18	16.61	10.22	8.32	1.00	0.90
36	22.47	14.05	13.30	16.30	9.80	7.75	0.00	0.95
37	22.47	14.05	13.30	17.05	10.17	8.19	0.00	0.85
38	22.47	14.05	13.30	16.92	10.11	8.11	0.00	1.08
39	22.47	14.06	13.21	16.92	10.11	8.03	0.00	0.90
40	19.97	12.81	11.51	14.26	7.82	5.64	0.00	1.08
41	19.97	12.81	11.52	15.01	8.20	6.08	0.00	1.15
42	19.97	12.81	11.51	15.01	8.20	6.08	0.00	1.26
43	20.85	13.22	12.04	14.56	7.93	5.76	0.00	1.18
44	20.85	13.22	12.02	16.07	8.68	6.58	0.00	1.11
45	21.67	14.40	12.78	16.11	9.13	6.66	0.00	1.00
46	19.97	12.81	11.53	14.96	8.45	6.62	0.00	1.04
47	19.97	12.83	11.45	14.96	8.46	6.56	0.00	0.85
48	22.42	14.13	12.99	16.14	8.96	7.00	0.00	0.95
49	20.68	13.33	11.76	15.68	8.58	6.22	0.00	0.78

ing of descriptors taken from a large pool. Often in an automated selection of descriptors, a descriptor will be discarded because it is highly correlated with another descriptor already selected. But what is important is not

Table 3. Correlation matrix showing correlation among various topological indices

Compd. log K_i	log K_i 1.0000	${}^0\chi$	${}^1\chi$	${}^2\chi$	${}^0\chi^v$	${}^1\chi^v$	${}^2\chi^v$	Ip ₁
${}^0\chi$	-0.5946	1.0000						
${}^1\chi$	-0.7224	0.9481	1.0000					
${}^2\chi$	-0.5595	0.9919	0.9340	1.0000				
${}^0\chi^v$	-0.5590	0.8588	0.8978	0.8547	1.0000			
${}^1\chi^v$	-0.4895	0.7567	0.8020	0.7698	0.9335	1.0000		
${}^2\chi^v$	-0.2431	0.6400	0.5898	0.6696	0.8152	0.9049	1.0000	
Ip ₁	0.2551	0.1319	0.0196	0.1770	0.1885	0.3967	0.5912	1.0000

whether the two descriptors parallel to each other, i.e. duplication of the same structural information, but whether they are in those parts that are important for structure-property-activity correlations. If they differ in the domain which is important for the property/activity considered, both descriptors should be retained and if they differ in parts that are not relevant for the correlation of the considered property/activity, one of them can be discarded.

Randic^{11,12} further stated that if a descriptor strongly correlates with another descriptor already used in a regression and such a descriptor in most studies should be discarded. For example, ${}^1\chi^v$ and ${}^2\chi^v$, ${}^1\chi^v$ often strongly correlate and in many structure-property-activity studies, ${}^2\chi^v$ has been discarded. This is not theoretically justified and despite the widespread practice should be stopped. Although two highly correlated descriptors overall depict the same features of molecular structure, it is important to recognize that even highly interrelated descriptors differ in some other structural traits. The difference between them may be relatively small, but nevertheless very important for structure-property regression. Randic further argued that the criteria for inclusion or exclusion of descriptors should not be based on parallelism between descriptors even if overwhelming, but should be based on whether the part in which two descriptors disagree is or is not relevant for the characterization of the property considered. On the basis of above mentioned reasons we have obtained various regression analysis using combinations of those parameters which are linearly correlated. Mono-parametric and bi-parametric models using maximum R^2 method were developed and are discussed below.

A mono-parametric model containing ${}^1\chi$ as the cor-

relating parameter is found statistically significant :

$$\log K_i = -0.1583 (\pm 0.0220) {}^1\chi + 3.2805 \quad (1)$$

$n = 49, Se = 0.1973, r = -0.7238, R^2 = 0.5238,$
 $F = 51.732, Q = 3.6685$

No other single descriptor gave statistically significant model.

When ${}^2\chi$ is added to the above model slight improvement in the quality of fit has been observed :

$$\log K_i = -0.3443 (\pm 0.0549) {}^1\chi + 0.1605 (\pm 0.0443) {}^2\chi + 3.7387 \quad (2)$$

$n = 49, Se = 0.1759, r = 0.7935, R^2 = 0.6296,$
 $F = 39.127, Q = 4.5110$

The combination of ${}^1\chi$, ${}^2\chi$ and ${}^0\chi^v$, gave the following model which shows significant improvement over model expressed by eq. (2). The R -value obtained for this model is 0.8121, which accounts for approximately 64% variance. The model is reported below :

$$\log K_i = -0.4114 (\pm 0.0631) {}^1\chi + 0.1516 (\pm 0.0431) {}^2\chi + 0.0741 (\pm 0.0373) {}^0\chi^v + 3.5582 \quad (3)$$

$n = 49, Se = 0.1705, R = 0.8121, R^2 = 0.6595,$
 $F = 29.062, Q = 4.7630$

Further addition of second-order valence connectivity to the above mentioned model shows some improvement in the R^2 -value. The model obtained is as below :

$$\log K_i = -0.4701 (\pm 0.0910) {}^1\chi + 0.1773 (\pm 0.0519) {}^2\chi + 0.1258 (\pm 0.0688) {}^0\chi^v - 0.0646 (\pm 0.0609) {}^2\chi^v + 3.5582 \quad (4)$$

$n = 49, Se = 0.1709, R = 0.8159, R^2 = 0.6656,$
 $F = 21.902, Q = 4.774$

A combination of ${}^1\chi$, ${}^2\chi$, ${}^0\chi^v$, ${}^2\chi^v$ with an indicator parameter resulted into a five-parametric model with $R^2 = 0.6948$. The model (5) is as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_i = & -0.4777 (\pm 0.0880) {}^1\chi \\ & + 0.1715 (\pm 0.0502) {}^2\chi \\ & + 0.1850 (\pm 0.0726) {}^0\chi^v \\ & - 0.1601 (\pm 0.0785) {}^2\chi^v \\ & + 0.1954 (\pm 0.0960) Ip_1 + 3.5210 \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

$$n = 49, Se = 0.1651, R = 0.8336, R^2 = 0.6948,$$

$$F = 19.599, Q = 5.0490$$

Another model was developed by treating compounds **8**, **22**, **23** and **34** as outliers. Compound **34** contains thienyl group and is the only compound in the present investigation having five membered ring. Compounds **22** and **23** contain highly electronegative attachments containing fluorine. Therefore, they may behave differently as for as their mechanism is concerned. Compound **8** contains PhCH₂-group at R. This attachment gives a different orientation to the compound and may be one of the reasons for its different behavior, however, it is very difficult to give any specific reason for their behavior.

A drastic improvement in R^2 -value (0.7214) has been

observed in the model (7) (Table 4) containing ${}^1\chi$ and ${}^2\chi^v$ as correlating parameters. When an indicator parameter is also added to this we observed significant improvement ($R^2 = 0.7491$) in the model (8) (Table 4). Addition of ${}^0\chi^v$ to this model resulted into a four-parametric model (9) (Table 4). The R^2 -value has been increased from 0.7491 to 0.7602. All these models are reported in Table 4. When ${}^2\chi^v$, is also added we obtained a five-parametric model. This model (10) is expressed as eq. (6).

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_i = & -0.4454 (\pm 0.0805) {}^1\chi \\ & + 0.1711 (\pm 0.0443) {}^2\chi \\ & + 0.1287 (\pm 0.0690) {}^0\chi^v \\ & - 0.1012 (\pm 0.0743) {}^2\chi^v \\ & + 0.1627 (\pm 0.0830) Ip_1 \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

$$n = 45, Se = 0.1391, R = 0.8781, R^2 = 0.7710,$$

$$F = 26.277, Q = 6.3127$$

The quality factor^{13,14} $Q (R/Se)$ of the five-parametric model (10) expressed as eq. (6) clearly indicates that model containing ${}^1\chi$, ${}^2\chi$, ${}^0\chi^v$, ${}^2\chi^v$ and Ip_1 as correlating parameters is the best model for modeling $\log K_i$ of the present set of compounds. To confirm our findings we have also calculated cross-validated parameters¹⁰ viz. PRESS, SSY,

Table 4. Quality of statistical parameters along with cross validated parameters for various models after deleting outliers

Model no.	Parameters used	Coefficient of variation	R^2_A	R^2	PRESS/SSY	S_{PRESS}	R^2_{cv}	E	PE	PSE
7	${}^1\chi$	0.1479	0.7082	0.7214	0.3861	0.1698	0.6139	47.22	0.0276	0.1641
8	${}^2\chi$	0.1421	0.7307	0.7491	0.3350	0.1631	0.6650	49.92	0.0249	0.1557
9	Ip_1	0.1406	0.7362	0.7602	0.3154	0.1615	0.6846	51.04	0.0237	0.1523
10 (Eq. (6))	${}^1\chi$ ${}^2\chi$ ${}^0\chi^v$ ${}^2\chi^v$ Ip_1	0.1391	0.7418	0.7711	0.2968	0.1598	0.7032	52.16	0.0227	0.1488

PRESS : Predicted Residual Sum of Squares, SSY : Sum of the Squares of the response, S_{PRESS} : Uncertainty of prediction, R^2_{cv} : Overall Predictive ability, PE : Predictive Error, PSE : Predictive Square Error.

Table 5. Comparison of estimated biological activity ($\log K_1$) with their observed values using best Model 10 (eq. (6))

Compd.	$\log K_1$		Residual
	Observed	Estimated	
1	1.88	1.99	-0.11
2	1.88	1.77	0.11
3	1.72	1.75	-0.03
4	1.04	1.24	-0.20
5	0.85	0.72	0.13
6	1.84	1.79	0.05
7	1.73	1.34	0.39
9	1.54	1.29	0.25
10	1.51	1.35	0.16
11	1.48	1.41	0.07
12	1.57	1.45	0.12
13	1.56	1.34	0.22
14	1.00	1.13	-0.13
15	1.08	1.13	-0.05
16	1.11	1.11	0.00
17	0.95	1.12	-0.17
18	1.04	0.98	0.06
19	1.00	0.95	0.05
20	0.90	0.95	-0.05
21	0.95	1.10	-0.15
24	1.11	1.34	-0.23
25	1.32	1.19	0.13
26	1.23	1.31	-0.08
27	0.90	0.78	0.12
28	1.08	1.11	-0.03
29	0.95	1.13	-0.18
30	0.78	1.13	-0.35
31	0.85	0.94	-0.09

Table-5 (contd.)

32	0.90	0.94	-0.04
33	0.85	0.80	0.05
35	0.90	0.94	-0.04
36	0.95	0.91	0.04
37	0.85	0.96	-0.11
38	1.08	0.95	0.13
39	0.90	0.94	-0.04
40	1.08	1.10	-0.02
41	1.15	1.16	-0.01
42	1.26	1.16	0.10
43	1.18	1.04	0.14
44	1.11	1.15	-0.04
45	1.00	0.75	0.25
46	1.04	1.10	-0.06
47	0.85	1.08	-0.23
48	0.95	0.87	0.08
49	0.78	1.04	-0.26

R^2_{cv} , S_{PRESS} , PE and PSE for the models. These values are reported in Table 4. Predictive residual sum of squares (PRESS) appears to be the most important cross validation parameter accounting for a good estimate of the real predictive error of the models. If its value is less than SSY (sum of squares of response value) then one can say that the model predicts better than chance and can be considered statistically significant. If the value of PRESS/SSY is less than 0.4 then the model is said to be statistically significant and are better than chance. In our case (Table 4), for all models PRESS/SSY is less than 0.4 and the value of PRESS is less than SSY clearly indicating

Fig. 1. Comparison of observed and estimated $\log K_1$ using Model (10) (eq. (6)).

that the models are statistically significant. The value of $R^2_{cv} > 0.6$ indicates an excellent model. The values of R^2_{cv} were also fairly high indicating that models are statistically reliable. However, R^2 and other statistical parameters specially R^2_{cv} ($= 0.7032$) suggest that the model (10) containing $^1\chi$, $^2\chi$, $^0\chi^v$, $^2\chi^v$ and Ip_1 as correlating parameters, expressed by eq. (6), is the best for modeling the activity of present set of compounds.

Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) : The predictive error of coefficient of correlation¹⁰ is another parameter which is used to decide the predictive power of the proposed models. We have calculated PE value of the best proposed model and is reported in Table 4. It is argued that if

- (a) $R < PE$; then correlation is not significant;
- (b) $R > PE$; several times (at least three times), then correlation is significant; and if
- (c) $R > 6PE$; then the correlation is definitely excellent.

The data presented in Table 4 indicates that R is much larger than $6PE$ indicating that the models discussed above possess high degree of correlation.

Conclusions :

Following conclusions may be drawn :

- (i) A negative sign of $^1\chi$ indicates that first order branching is not favourable for exhibition of $\log K_1$ activity. It means that molecules having lesser branching should be chosen for better inhibitory activity.
- (ii) The $^2\chi^v$ variable is related to the degree of skeletal branching, increases as the amount of branching increases within a molecule. This index also increases with the number and complexity of rings. A negative coefficient of $^2\chi^v$ indicates that a smaller index value is related to lesser toxicity.
- (iii) A positive sign of zero-order valence connecti-

vity suggests that molecules having lesser branching and substituted with halogens will increase the activity.

(iv) A positive sign of Ip_1 suggests that the derivatives of structure A will act as good inhibitors. Therefore, the future designing with this structure should be tried.

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